

Stakeholders and Hydrogen: Insights from a Cross-Country Dialogue on Social

Acceptance

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Abstract

The workshop “*Social Acceptance & Public Engagement of Green Hydrogen in the Energy Transition*” was organised as part of the Benelux Hydrogen Knowledge Exchange event, held on November 18th, 2025, in Groningen, the Netherlands. The event was jointly hosted by LuxHyVal and HEAVENN to strengthen cooperation across the Benelux (Luxembourg, Belgium, and the Netherlands) hydrogen ecosystem, encouraging knowledge exchange, networking, and collaborative learning. The workshop provided a space for participants from different countries and professional backgrounds to engage with current challenges and practical approaches to fostering social acceptance and public engagement regarding green hydrogen. Methodologically, the workshop combined interactive quizzes, lightning talks, and a World Café format, demonstrating the value of mixed participatory approaches for exploring stakeholder perspectives. The findings show that social acceptance and public engagement are perceived as dynamic and context-dependent processes, linked to trust, perceived risks, communication quality, fairness, and socio-economic benefits. These dynamics appear particularly fragile at the local level, where proximity to infrastructure intensifies safety concerns and the role of perceived risk. At the same time, cross-national differences underline the importance of international exchange and mutual learning for understanding how institutional settings and political cultures play a role in acceptance and engagement processes.

Beyond documenting workshop outcomes, this report provides empirically grounded, practice-relevant insights to support policymakers and project developers in advancing socially accepted hydrogen deployment.

Keywords: Social acceptance, public engagement, green hydrogen, stakeholder dialogue, cross-border cooperation

Background and Goals of the Workshop

The workshop aimed to explore and strengthen the understanding of social acceptance and public engagement in the context of green hydrogen deployment. More specifically, workshop attendees reflected on key influencing factors, including trust in institutions and project developers, perceived fairness of decision-making processes, quality of communication and information sharing, and risks and benefits associated with green hydrogen solutions. A key part of the workshop focused on sharing experiences and good practices from ongoing hydrogen projects aimed at improving public engagement and social acceptance, with particular attention to initiatives in the Benelux countries (Belgium, the Netherlands, and Luxembourg). Ultimately, stakeholders identified strategies for fostering meaningful engagement and acceptance, taking into account both local needs and broader socio-political contexts. Cross-country and cross-sector learning proved central to developing innovative and socially responsible approaches to green hydrogen deployment. The workshop also sought to connect stakeholder perspectives with actionable insights for policy and practice.

Structure of the Workshop

The workshop was divided into two main parts and lasted two hours. The first part, interactive quiz & lightning talks, featured an interactive quiz designed to introduce key concepts in social acceptance and public engagement. Participants were invited to answer short questions displayed on the screen using a QR code and observe the live results on screen,

offering immediate collective reflection on shared perceptions and differences across the group. All responses were recorded anonymously. Following the quiz, the moderators delivered a series of lightning talks, which offered insights into theories, methods, current research, and practical experiences. Specifically, these talks were focused on ongoing green hydrogen projects: Luxembourg Hydrogen Valley (LuxHyVal - Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement No. 101111984) and EnAqua-Dialog (BMW-funded research project, No. 03EI5264C). The goal was to provide concrete examples of how social acceptance and public engagement in regional or local green hydrogen projects can be systematically studied and integrated into real-world energy transitions. In detail, LuxHyVal, coordinated by the University of Luxembourg, aims to develop the country's first national hydrogen valley. Within this broader initiative, the workshop contributed by highlighting the social dimension of hydrogen deployment, showing how public perceptions, trust-building, and engagement processes are essential components in technological and infrastructural development. The second example, EnAqua-Dialog, coordinated by the Fraunhofer Institute for Environmental, Safety, and Energy Technology (UMSICHT), provided a perspective on stakeholder engagement. This transdisciplinary project develops an adaptive dialogue format, enabling in-person and online participation formats. Its goal is to facilitate structured interaction among local authorities and sectoral stakeholders in the energy transition. In the workshop, EnAqua-Dialog illustrated how co-creation sessions, iterative consultations, and continuous exchange with local actors help build trust, transparency, and more inclusive and accepted decision-making processes.

The second part of the workshop followed a World Café format designed to stimulate open dialogue and collective reflection, as well as a social collaborative learning environment among participants. Three posters were set up in the room, each featuring a different guiding question related to the workshop's themes. Participants rotated between the posters in small

groups (12-14 participants), spending approximately ten minutes at each station. During every rotation, participants were invited to share their thoughts, concerns, and experiences by writing them on post-it notes and placing them directly on the poster. The atmosphere was intentionally informal: there were no right or wrong answers, and the goal was to encourage open exchange, listen to different perspectives, and build on each other's contributions. A designated note-taker remained at each poster throughout the entire session to ensure continuity and capture key points from each group. After all rotations were completed, the three note-takers provided a five-minute summary of the main insights and takeaways emerging from their respective groups. The World Café session concluded with a general reflection and an open discussion, allowing participants to connect ideas across tables, clarify points, and highlight potential areas for further exploration or collaboration.

Participants

The workshop was attended by $N = 38$ participants. Participants included representatives from academic/university ($n = 15$), energy and mobility providers ($n = 9$), industry and private companies ($n = 5$), research institutions ($n = 4$), public authorities and regional agencies ($n = 3$), and other organisations ($n = 2$). This diverse attendance of international participants and cross-sectional stakeholders ensured a wide range of expertise and experiences in the discussions, providing rich qualitative insights into stakeholder perspectives, although it was not intended to be statistically representative.

To gain an overview of participants' backgrounds and their familiarity with the topics of social acceptance and public engagement, the workshop began with two open questions: *In your professional role, how regularly do you address matters concerning social acceptance?* And *In your professional role, how regularly do you address matters concerning public engagement?* (answer options: *regularly – it's part of my daily work, occasionally – I've been involved in some activities, rarely – it's not a main focus, but I'm interested, not yet – I'm new*

to this topic, not applicable to my current role/none of the above). The responses showed that 12% address matters concerning social acceptance in their professional role regularly, 32% occasionally, and 40% rarely or have not addressed it yet. Regarding the encounter of public engagement in their professional role, the majority of participants rarely address this topic in their job (36%). 32% of the participants address this matter occasionally, whereas 16% address public engagement regularly in their professional role. These results indicate that while social acceptance and public engagement are recognised topics in both research and practice, they are not yet fully integrated into the daily routines of many professionals involved in hydrogen or energy-related activities. This distribution also highlights the relevance of knowledge exchange formats, which can support learning and cross-sector dialogue.

Part 1: Interactive Quiz & Lightning Talks

Methodology

Empirical insights into participants' perceptions of social acceptance and public engagement were generated in the first part of the workshop. The responses to six interactive questions (three on social acceptance and three on public engagement) were analysed and interpreted by focusing on the frequency of words, their semantic meaning, and their valence (positive, negative, neutral terms). The analyses were supported by R-based text processing functions, which enabled the systematic extraction and aggregation of keywords for interpretation, and the Word Cloud software for the frequency of words. This approach allowed identifying dominant themes and underlying affective orientations associated with social acceptance and public engagement, as conceptualised within socio-political, discursive, and place-based perspectives (Batel et al., 2020; Devine-Wright, 2009; Wolsink, 2018).

Social acceptance in Green Hydrogen Projects

To open the first part of the workshop, the question: *What is the first word that comes to your mind when you think about social acceptance?* was asked, which served to assess the audience's initial awareness and capture spontaneous associations with the concept.

The session continued with the lighting talks, providing an overview of social acceptance, defined as a positive response (including attitudes, intentions, behaviours, and actual use) towards a specific technology or socio-technical system within a given social unit (Upham et al., 2015). The multilevel nature of social acceptance was illustrated using the dynamic perspectives of the “triangle of social acceptance” (socio-political, community, and market acceptance), underlining temporal, spatial, and power-related dimensions (Ellis et al., 2023). The session further emphasised the context-specificity of social acceptance, influenced by local experiences, governance processes, communication, and perceived fairness. Then, the cognitive components (beliefs, knowledge, perceived risks, and benefits) and affective dimensions (emotions, values, and identity) of the topic have been presented. Finally, to illustrate practical approaches, the session outlined a range of social science methods, including qualitative (e.g., interviews, focus groups, etc.) and quantitative approaches (e.g., surveys, experiments, etc.), media and discourse analysis (e.g., content and frame analysis, social media studies, etc.), as well as mixed and participatory methods (e.g., multi-stakeholder dialogues).

Case Study Illustrating Real-World Application. The session illustrated real-world applications, presenting the LuxHyVal project, particularly focusing on Work Package 6: Comprehensive Impact Assessment and Public Acceptance, led by the Environmental Psychology Department at the Institute for Future Energy and Material Flow Systems (IZES gGmbH). The work package approach aims to study social context through stakeholder mapping, expert interviews, and surveys to identify local needs, expectations, and concerns. This interactive session started with a question: *How would you rate the importance of*

community acceptance in relation to green hydrogen projects in your region? (answer options: *very important, rather important, neutral, rather unimportant, very unimportant*).

Then, participants were invited to reflect on the key aspects of meaningful community acceptance with an open question: *In your opinion, what are the key aspects of meaningful community acceptance in green hydrogen projects in your region?*. Then, some insights have been presented, such as trust (Siegrist, 2000), fairness (Wolsink, 2018), perceived benefits and costs (Wolsink, 2018), risk perception (Hildebrand et al., 2025), perceived efficacy and control (Huijts et al., 2009), place attachment and identity (Devine-Wright, 2014), and social and personal norms (Bamberg et al., 2015).

The workshop then provided an overview of qualitative empirical insights derived from stakeholder analysis and expert interviews ($N = 10$) conducted in Luxembourg. These interviews offered contextual perspectives, revealing that green hydrogen is still perceived as an abstract concept by the general public and that existing knowledge gaps and confusion may slow down acceptance processes. At the same time, dialogue among stakeholders, visible government support, and concrete pilot projects were identified as key enablers of trust. Experts also emphasised that perceived risks, particularly related to costs and health, require proactive, transparent communication strategies (Vespa & Hildebrand, 2025).

Finally, the workshop introduced the ongoing national survey in Luxembourg as a quantitative extension of these insights. Participants were given an overview of the survey design, which adopts a multilingual approach (English, German, French, and Luxembourgish) and systematically examines cognitive, emotional, and social-normative dimensions of public perception. With 1,070 valid responses currently under analysis, the survey explores the interactions between knowledge, trust, perceived risks, benefits, and social norms, providing an empirical basis for identifying population needs, expectations, and concerns. Presenting the

LuxHyVal project and related activities allowed participants to get empirical insights and emerging patterns in public perceptions of green hydrogen in a real national context.

Key Findings. The above-mentioned questions are illustrated in Figure 1, in which the most frequent spontaneous associations with the concept of social acceptance are shown. The recurrence of the terms “involvement”, “public awareness”, “reliability”, and especially “challenges” suggests that social acceptance is perceived as a multidimensional and evolving process, influenced by institutional trust, communication practices, and perceived uncertainties. In detail, the centrality of “challenge(s)” reflects an awareness of barriers, combined with “misunderstanding”, “resistance”, “fear”, and “potential protest”, that accompany energy projects and need to be managed through responsibility and cooperation. At the same time, terms such as “dialogue”, “consensus”, and “progress” indicate that participants also associate social acceptance with relational and communicative processes.

Figure 1.

Word cloud of word associations: What is the first word that comes to your mind when you think about social acceptance?

Following, attention was directed toward community acceptance, with a specific focus on the local context. Figure 2 shows participants’ assessment of the importance of community acceptance in relation to green hydrogen projects. The results displayed that eight participants rated community acceptance as rather important (32%), and 11 participants considered

community acceptance as very important (44%). Based on the relatively low percentage of participants rating community acceptance as unimportant (4%) or neutral (8%), it can therefore be assumed that this issue is considered (rather) valuable, which underlines the significance of further exploring and elaborating community acceptance with the broader public and stakeholders.

Figure 2.

Distribution of responses: How would you rate the importance of community acceptance in relation to green hydrogen projects in your region?

Finally, participants were asked an open-ended question to identify key aspects of meaningful community acceptance in green hydrogen projects in their region (see Figure 3). In detail, community acceptance was linked to aspects related to trust, reliability, and perceived value. In particular, terms such as “reliability”, “public value”, and “support from the public” appear recurrently, suggesting that participants consider the credibility of projects and their tangible benefits for the community as central factors for acceptance. Furthermore, transparent

and effective communication emerges as a key element. References to “communication”, “digestible information”, and “languages” indicate that participants need accessible and understandable information to reduce uncertainty and misunderstandings surrounding technologies. Words such as “engagement”, “stage involvement”, and “social groups” suggest that there is a need to actively involve communities throughout different phases of the project. This also reflects the importance of early involvement and high awareness in building long-term support. Finally, the emphasis on “degree of usefulness” and “affordability” indicates that community acceptance depends not only on environmental benefits but also if projects are perceived as economically accessible and beneficial at the local level.

Figure 3.

Word cloud of word associations: In your opinion, what are the key aspects of meaningful community acceptance in green hydrogen projects in your region?

Public Engagement in Green Hydrogen Projects

The next section of the workshop started by introducing and describing the topic of public engagement while including some practical and theoretical insights. To engage the participants to share their first thoughts connected to public engagement, the open question: *What is the first word that comes to your mind when you think about public engagement?* was asked.

The session continued with lightning talks, providing information on public engagement, defined as the assortment of different communicative methods that must take

place to ensure the stakeholders' involvement or lessen their oppositional attitudes towards a specific issue or topic, i.e., to eventually foster acceptance (Bourne, 2016). Overall, a connection between engagement and acceptance can be assumed, but should not be interpreted as the only supporting factor in acceptance (e.g., Hildebrand et al., 2017a). Then, during the session, the pyramid displaying the levels of participation (Rau et al., 2012) was presented to discuss the four engagement approaches for increasing engagement. The model highlights different degrees of participation, depending on the context and the necessity, i.e., some contexts expect higher or lower degrees of participation as well as different perspectives (involving persons and participants). Ranging from "information", as the lowest level of participation, to "engagement/responsibility", as the highest level of participation, the implementation of the right level of engagement in the specific context is indispensable.

Case Study Illustrating Real-World Application. The lightning talk on EnAqua-Dialog intended to display the relevance of valid and impactful engagement among stakeholders. The project EnAqua-Dialog aims to design and carry out an adaptive dialogue process for implementation projects using the example of regional hydrogen hubs (Ostfriesland and Sauerland in Germany). Specifically, the objective is to bring conflicts surrounding water out into the open and defuse them. The Department of Environmental Psychology at IZES gGmbH is leading Work Package 5: Social Science Support, Evaluation of Methodology, and Transfer, which focuses on the evaluation and optimisation of the process and methodology used. To open this part, the participants were asked: *How would you rate the importance of stakeholder engagement in relation to green hydrogen projects in your region* (answer options: *very important, rather important, neutral, rather unimportant, very unimportant*).

Participants were then asked to reflect on key aspects of meaningful community engagement in green hydrogen projects in their regions (*In your opinion, what are the key aspects of meaningful community engagement in green hydrogen projects in your region?*).

After, some key aspects based on scientific literature, such as transparency, a balanced representation of stakeholders (Hildebrand et al., 2017b), trust (Trammell et al., 2025), and early involvement (De Weger et al., 2018) were presented. To complement these conceptual foundations, the workshop also provided an overview of stakeholder perspectives. Furthermore, to gain deeper insights into stakeholders' views and opinions, the interviews conducted in the EnAqua-Dialog project ($N = 15$) were presented, focusing on the identification of regional conflicts, key stakeholders, and public perceptions. Some detected conflicts, for example, included inadequate communication and information deficits. The results further showed that continuous evaluation of the engagement process is essential to identify opportunities, potential barriers, and best practices for effective participation. Then, a tailored schedule of online questionnaires was implemented to examine whether the designed participation process is a valid and promising method to engage stakeholders.

Key Findings. Figure 4 illustrates the most frequent spontaneous associations with the concept of public engagement. The terms “face-to-face-interactions”, “social media”, “newspapers”, and “science communication” indicate communicative channels that structure and mediate. Furthermore, participants reported “trust”, “commitment”, and “responsibility” as essential for successful public engagement. Levels of engagement, referring to the depth of the involvement, were identified in terms of “participation”, “consultation”, “education”, and “ambassadorship”. Participants further pointed out some desirable outcomes such as “added value”, “social acceptance”, and “life quality improvement”. Some perceived barriers and critical perspectives in words like “low” or “difficult” were perceived, as well as “what’s in it for me?”, emphasising the scepticism towards benefits.

Figure 4.

Word cloud of word associations: What is the first word that comes to your mind when you think about public engagement?

To assess the participants’ rating of the importance of stakeholder engagement in relation to green hydrogen projects, the question: *How would you rate the importance of stakeholder engagement in relation to green hydrogen projects in your region?* was asked. Most of the participants regarded stakeholder engagement as rather important (36%) or very important (36%), indicating the high relevance of this topic. A small part of respondents expressed neutral or low evaluations of the importance of public engagement, with 4% indicating a neutral position and 8% rating it as rather unimportant and unimportant (4% each). These results reveal that the majority of participants consider stakeholder engagement in relation to green hydrogen projects as important, which further indicates and highlights the validity of investigating this topic. When comparing the results regarding social acceptance in green hydrogen projects, more participants rated social acceptance as more important than public engagement (44% vs. 36%). This suggests that participants may perceive social acceptance as a prerequisite for project success, while viewing public engagement more as a supporting or instrumental process. This aspect needs further investigation to better understand how stakeholders conceptualise the relationship between engagement and acceptance, and how this may influence the design of participation strategies in hydrogen projects.

Figure 5.

Distribution of responses: How would you rate the importance of public engagement in relation to green hydrogen projects in your region?

Lastly, participants were asked an open-ended question to identify key aspects of meaningful stakeholder engagement in green hydrogen projects in their region (see Figure 6). First, participants mentioned “education”, “publicity”, “awareness”, and “communication” as key aspects of successful engagement, indicating that information and early involvement are considered essential preconditions for participation. The reference to the term “informed society pushing for progress” further highlights the importance of the involvement of citizens and stakeholders. Furthermore, active participation is desired, which can be implemented by “involvement”, “influencing decisions”, and “local politics”. Some economic, financial, and ethical aspects were addressed, such as “economic opportunities”, “value growth”, and “fairness”, suggesting the wish for shared value and equity. Finally, by mentioning “evidence”, the participants demand trust through data and scientific evidence.

Figure 6.

Word cloud of word associations: In your opinion, what are the key aspects of meaningful stakeholder engagement in green hydrogen projects in your region?

Part 2: World Café Posters

Methodology

The World Café session was conducted to facilitate collaborative dialogue and collective reflection among participants, creating a social learning environment where diverse perspectives could be shared and discussed (Brown & Isaacs, 2005; Ropes et al., 2020). Three posters were prepared, each corresponding to a specific guiding question: (1) Relevance of Acceptance – exploring the main factors (enablers and obstacles) influencing social acceptance of green hydrogen projects in participants’ contexts; (2) Engagement Strategies – collecting experiences and insights on how stakeholders can be effectively involved in energy projects beyond standard consultation; (3) Learning Across Borders – identifying differences in challenges and opportunities for social acceptance and public engagement across countries.

The data collected from the posters were analysed thematically, with keywords and recurring concepts extracted to identify dominant themes. In addition, attention was given to the semantic valence and frequency of terms, providing a descriptive overview of participants’ perceptions and opinions regarding social acceptance and public engagement. This approach follows established methods for participatory workshops and collaborative knowledge

elicitation, combining qualitative insights with structured visualisation to support interpretation (Visser et al., 2005). The keywords generated during the poster discussions were grouped into three clusters, with the original terms written by participants reported in the Results section in quotation marks.

Key Findings

Relevance of Acceptance: What are the main factors (enablers and obstacles) that influence social acceptance of green hydrogen projects in your context?

Factors supporting social acceptance: Participants highlighted the importance of “clear and open communication and information” on benefits and long-term implications. “Trust-building” emerged as a central element, both toward institutions and actors working within the energy sector. “Education”, “public investment”, and “visible infrastructure” were also considered relevant factors, besides “solar and wind as an example to see it as the future”, because they are perceived as familiar reference points. Additional positive aspects were “energy independence”, “efficiency”, and “opportunities for local or self-production of energy”.

Barriers and challenges: Participants included perceived “risks”, “high prices”, “concerns about efficiency”, “greenwashing”, and “fears related to job displacement or sectoral change” as obstacles. Plus, they also pointed to “misinformation” and “disinformation”, as well as the “strategic use of knowledge gaps” to manipulate public opinion. “Low levels of education” and “limited public awareness” were seen as further challenges, which could reinforce resistance.

Structural and societal factors: Participants emphasised broader societal and structural aspects like “public control over infrastructure”, “long-term investments”, “societal mindsets” toward energy transitions, and the importance of “real and tangible” projects that people can see and interact with. Acceptance challenges were described as particularly pronounced at the

“local level”, where proximity to hydrogen production or industrial facilities intensifies concerns related to “safety, health, and everyday life”.

Engagement Strategies: In your experience, how can stakeholders be effectively involved in energy projects, beyond simple consultation?

Forms of participation and involvement: Participants proposed a wide range of participatory formats, including “workshops”, “co-creation activities”, and “site visits”. “Financial participation” mechanisms (such as “direct investment” and “revenue sharing”) were mentioned as ways to strengthen engagement and ownership. “Ambassadors” and “peer-to-peer” approaches were also highlighted. Participants stressed that engagement becomes credible only when stakeholders are “taken seriously”, granted “actual responsibilities”, and involved in decision-making and policy processes. Being “listened to, receiving feedback, and seeing tangible outcomes” from participation were described as essential for sustaining trust and long-term engagement.

Communication and dialogue tools: Effective engagement was closely linked to “targeted and comprehensible communication”. Participants stressed the need for public communication that is adapted to specific target groups, including “digestible reports” and “follow-up on ideas”. “Social media” and “public debates” were mentioned as additional tools for fostering dialogue.

Socio-economic incentives and regional value creation: Engagement strategies were linked to broader socio-economic benefits, such as the creation of “regional value” and “energy independence”. These aspects were seen as important motivators for sustained participation.

Learning Across Borders: How do challenges and opportunities for social acceptance and public engagement differ across your countries?

Institutional and governance factors: Participants discussed variations in “trust in government”, levels of “corruption”, regulatory frameworks, and questions of responsibility

between companies, governments, and citizens, indicating a possible threat to the energy transition and the hydrogen economy. Institutional reliability and governance capacity were identified as key factors shaping acceptance across national contexts.

Socio-cultural contexts and economic dynamics: “Historical experiences”, “societal values”, and prevailing consumption patterns were mentioned as influencing how energy transitions are perceived. Differences in societal mindsets and “triggers for change” were seen as shaping openness or resistance to hydrogen projects. Cross-border differences were also linked to “geopolitical strategies”, “resource availability”, “production costs”, and “security considerations”. Participants highlighted that opportunities and challenges are embedded in broader European and global energy dynamics (“knowledge does not stop at the border”), suggesting a reciprocal learning opportunity, especially for emerging market countries where the expansion of renewable energies is anticipated.

Conflict, protest, and participation: Participants reflected on differing forms of “protest” as a communication channel and participation, ranging from peaceful to disruptive actions due to pressure of political will. “Inclusion”, “legitimacy”, and “public trust” were seen as critical factors in shaping how conflicts unfold across countries.

Discussion

The workshop findings highlight that social acceptance and public engagement are recognised as key dimensions of green hydrogen deployment. Across interactive quizzes, lightning talks, and World Café discussions, participants framed acceptance as a dynamic, multi-level, and context-dependent process. In detail, the workshop aligns with risk perception and trust research (Siegrist, 2000) by emphasising how hydrogen-specific imaginaries can influence acceptance, particularly in contexts where technical knowledge remains limited. These imaginaries are mitigated through communication, education, and everyday visibility, supporting the view that acceptance evolves through learning and social normalisation over

time (Devine-Wright, 2009). In this sense, communication transmits information but also influences how hydrogen technologies are framed and emotionally evaluated by different audiences. Building on research on energy communication, acceptance processes are affected not only by cognitive assessments (e.g., knowledge, perceived risks, and benefits) but also by affective responses such as hope, concern, fear, or pride (Vespa et al., 2022). Thus, risk communication should explicitly address fears related to safety, health, and industrial proximity topics. Transparent comparisons with other energy technologies, combined with visible demonstration projects, can help shift perceptions from abstract risk to concrete experience.

Concerning public engagement, during the workshop, participants underlined the relevance of involvement strategies perceived as credible, combining procedural elements (e.g., being heard, co-decision, etc.) with material dimensions (e.g., financial participation, jobs, regional value creation, etc.). Importantly, the cross-border perspective suggests that acceptance and engagement practices are highly context-dependent and cannot be directly transferred across settings. However, to prevent political instability in emerging market countries, the EU is required to pair its energy infrastructure projects with significant investments in local education. Thus, project developers and policymakers should adapt approaches to national and regional institutional settings, levels of trust, and cultural expectations. In this sense, workshops and events function as boundary spaces for mutual learning, reflexivity, and the co-production of social energy solutions. The results also support procedural justice theories (Gross, 2007) by showing that acceptance is closely linked to how decisions are made and communicated. Furthermore, participants stressed that transparent processes, early involvement, and visible responsiveness are essential for trust-building. This finding is in line with recent work emphasising legitimacy and fairness as central mechanisms in energy transitions (Jenkins et al., 2021; Wolsink, 2018). In practice, engagement strategies

should prioritise meaningful participation and empowerment (Arnstein, 1969). This supports recent policy-oriented research highlighting the importance of moving from participation “*in form*” to participation “*in substance*” (De Weger et al., 2018; Trammell et al., 2025).

Recommendations and Conclusions

Based on the insights generated during the workshop, the following recommendations can be formulated:

(a) Proactively address safety concerns and risk perceptions through transparent communication.

Communication and engagement strategies should explicitly address safety concerns and risk perceptions, particularly in communities located close to hydrogen infrastructure. Transparent discussion of risks, uncertainties, and mitigation measures is essential for trust-building.

(b) Enable meaningful participation with clear feedback loops and tangible outcomes.

Public engagement should enable stakeholders to influence decisions, receive feedback, and see tangible outcomes. Co-creation formats and financial participation mechanisms can raise credibility and long-term commitment.

(c) Link hydrogen projects to visible local benefits.

Acceptance is more likely when green hydrogen projects are linked to tangible positive outcomes such as energy independence, regional value creation, employment opportunities, and affordable energy. Demonstration projects and visible applications can support learning and familiarity.

(d) Address distributional concerns and transition-related impacts early on.

Concerns related to cost distribution, job security, and sectoral change should be addressed proactively. Engagement processes should explicitly consider how benefits and burdens are shared across communities and stakeholder groups.

(e) Design context-sensitive engagement strategies supported by continuous evaluation.

Engagement strategies should be tailored to local, regional, and national contexts. Continuous evaluation and iterative adaptation of participation processes can help identify barriers, opportunities, and best practices.

Competing interests

No competing interests were disclosed.

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